

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on the Knowledge Regarding Menstrual Hygiene among Women of Child Bearing Age in a Selected Community of Rewa (M. P.).

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Abstract:-

Introduction: Menstrual hygiene refers to the private hygiene exercise in the course of menstruation. A lady wants to exercise an excessive degree of non-public hygiene at some point of her durations and the private hygiene begins from the resolution of high-quality sanitary products, its perfect usage, disposal, physique cleanliness, diet, etc. Menstrual hygiene is necessary due to the fact it is a herbal method of hygiene associated to exercise of female in the course of menstruation as it has an effect in phrases of to stop reproductive tract infections and urinary tract infections. **Aim:** The goal of the find out about is to determine the effectiveness of structured instructing programme on the know-how concerning menstrual hygiene amongst female of toddler bearing age in selected neighborhood of Rewa (M. P.). **Methods:** The conceptual framework in this find out about is primarily based on King's Goal attainment theory, (King Imogene, 1981). The lookup graph chosen for the find out about is the pre-experimental one-group pre-test post-test design. Convenient sampling method was once used to acquire the data. Total 50 female of infant bearing age have been chosen for the lookup learn about residing in Urrahat community, Rewa (M. P.). Self-structured questionnaire used to be organized to verify the know-how of ladies of toddler bearing age concerning menstrual hygiene. In this learn about impartial variable used to be structured instructing programme organized by using the researcher and structured variables used to be understanding of the sample. **Result:** Mean pre- check rating of ladies of infant bearing age was once 6.9 and imply post-test rating used to be 25.42 with the suggest distinction of 19. The computed 't' test (-33.77 P .000) confirmed that there used to be a tremendously big distinction between pre-test and post-test expertise score. There used to be no giant affiliation between age, kind of family, religion, month-to-month earnings of the family, age at your menstruation started out and supply of statistics and pre-test score. There was once substantial affiliation between instructional popularity and pre-test score. **Conclusion:** The findings of the existing find out about confirmed that the imply post-test expertise rating

(25.42) is greater than the suggest pre-test know-how rating (6.9). Hence the lookup speculation H2 is accepted. This suggests that an structured educating programme is advantageous in growing the understanding rating amongst ladies of toddler bearing age related to menstrual hygiene.

Keywords:- Menstruation, Menstrual Hygiene, Effectiveness.

I. INTRODUCTION

Menstruation is a natural, everyday organic method skilled by way of all adolescent female and women, but it is now not spoken about overtly inflicting needless embarrassment and shame. India's 113 million adolescent ladies are mainly prone at the onset of menarche. At this time, they want a secure surroundings that provides safety and coaching to make sure their primary health, well-being and instructional chance is realised.

The ordinary menstrual cycle in girls represents a complicated aggregate of hormones such as estrogen and progesterone. The menstrual cycle typically takes place each 28-35 days $\pm$ 2-3 days the place the menstrual go with the flow lasts for 3-5 days with a loss of between 30-80 ml of blood.

A latest find out about determined that in 14,724 public faculties solely 53% had a separate and usable lady toilet. 1 At domestic the state of affairs wants to be expanded and with 132 million households besides a lavatory (2015), it leaves ladies and younger girls going through the disgrace of specific liberation. However, secure and positive menstrual hygiene management, or 'MHM', is the reason of higher and more suitable improvement for women and younger women.

➤ Need of The Study

Girls can begin menstruating at the age of 9 and up to sixteen years. The common age for a woman to begin menstruating is 12 years. As it is very early in the morning for female they would now not be bodily and mentally organized for menstruation. When women get their period, they experience embarrassed about exposing even their mothers.

There will be fewer probabilities of retaining hygiene at some point of menstruation due to the fact the trouble is now not being mentioned in nuclear families. Even modern women who get media data can't be used actually besides being defined.

Menstruation and associated troubles are hardly ever mentioned with young adults and their parents. If they have a excellent understanding of menstruation and menstrual hygiene most of the childhood troubles will be solved.

➤ *Statement of The Problem*

“A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on the knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among women of child bearing age in a selected community of Rewa (M. P.)”

➤ *Objectives*

- 1) To assess the pre-test knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among women of child bearing age.
- 2) To assess the post-test knowledge regarding the menstrual hygiene among women of child bearing age.
- 3) To determine the effectiveness of the structured teaching programme on the knowledge regarding the menstrual hygiene among women of child bearing age.
- 4) To find out the association between pre-test knowledge and selected socio- demographic variables.

➤ *Hypothesis*

H1 - There will be a significant relationship between knowledge levels of the women of child bearing age regarding menstrual hygiene with selected socio-demographic variables.

H2 – There will be a significant increase in the mean post-test knowledge score than the mean pre-test knowledge score.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A quantitative research method used to be viewed the quality to examine the information of girls of childbearing age concerning menstrual hygiene The lookup layout chosen for the find out about is the pre-experimental one-group pretest-post-test design. This plan is broadly used in instructional research. P.E – Pre-Experimental Group 01 – Pre-test knowledge score X - Treatment Variable (Structured teaching programme) 02 - Post-test knowledge score

➤ *Independent Variable*

The impartial variable is the circumstance or traits manipulated by using the research. In the existing find out about the impartial variable is the structured educating programme related to the information of menstrual hygiene amongst girls of baby bearing age. In the current learn about based variable refers to the understanding of girls of infant bearing age related to the menstrual hygiene The on hand populace is that team that is truly reachable for the learn about by way of the researcher. By figuring out the population, the teacher-researcher makes clear the crew to which the find out about consequences can be utilized The pattern for this learn about comprised of 50 girls of

toddler bearing age. In this study, the pattern was once chosen via a non-probability handy sampling method due to the fact of the restricted quantity of time and availability of topics in accordance to the sampling criteria. Ward no. 13, Urrahat neighborhood protected a populace of 50 samples. A structured understanding questionnaire was once organized for assessing the understanding about the menstrual hygiene amongst ladies of infant bearing age. It was once based totally on the literature extracted from journals, books, lookup reports, non-public experience, peer team discussion, and specialist guidance.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1:- Distribution of Pre-test according to Frequency and Percentage

Pre test	Frequency	Percent
Poor	44	88.0
Average	6	12.0
Good	0	0
Total	50	100.0

Table 2:- Distribution of Post-test according to Frequency and Percentage

Post test	Frequency	Percent
Poor	0	0
Average	7	14.0
Good	43	86.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 3:- Mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ value of pre-test and post-test knowledge score

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t	df	P value	Significance
Pre test	6.9000	50	2.51729	-	49	.000*	S
Post test	25.4200	50	3.56908	33.779			

The statistics introduced in Table No. 4.10 and Fig 4.10 suggests that the imply post- take a look at expertise rating (25.42) is interestingly greater than the imply pretest expertise rating (6.9). The disruption of post-test rankings (SD 3.56 is greater than that of their pre- check ratings (SD 2.51) and the computed ‘t’ cost indicates that there is a sizeable distinction between pretest and post-test imply information rating (t = 33.77). This suggests that the Structured educating programme was once superb in growing the information of female of childbearing age involving menstrual hygiene

Thus, the hypothesis H2 is accepted.

*P value is significant at P<0.05

As per affiliation between pre-test expertise rating and demographic data, instructional popularity is related with pre-test know-how rating whereas age, kind of family, religion, month-to-month profits of the family, age at your menstruation

commenced and supply of records is no longer related with pre-test understanding score.

Hence, hypothesis H1 was accepted.

IV. SUMMARY

Descriptive and inferential data have been used for analysis. In the Pre-test majority of the pattern forty eight had terrible expertise score, whereas in the put up check majority of the pattern forty six had Good understanding and the Mean Post-test rating used to be 25.42 which was once substantially greater than imply pre-test expertise rating 6.9.

As per affiliation between pre-test information rating and demographic data, academic popularity is related with pre-test understanding rating whereas age, kind of family, religion, month-to-month earnings of the family, age at your menstruation began and supply of statistics is now not related with pre-test information score.

V. CONCLUSION

From the findings of the find out about it is clear that the ladies of baby bearing age had a terrible information rating and additionally the learn about decided the affiliation between pre-check know-how rating and demographic variables.

1. The existing learns about printed that the girls of baby bearing age had a terrible know-how score.
2. The current learn about published that the ladies of toddler bearing age had a proper know-how rating after they have been brought with structured instructing programme. Thus, structured instructing programme is wonderful in growing the information concerning menstrual hygiene.
3. There is vast affiliation between information rating and socio- demographic variables.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Annamma Jacob, - A Comprehensive Text Book of Midwifery, Jaypee Brothers Medical Publisher (P) Ltd., New Delhi, 2005.
- [2]. Abdella. F.G. & Levine, Better Nursing Care through Nursing Research, London; Mc Millian Company, 1986.
- [3]. Basavanthappa. B.T. Text Book of Nursing Research, New Delhi, Jaypee Brothers; New Delhi, 1998.
- [4]. Bobak. M.I. Lowdermilk. L.D. et al. Maternity Nursing, Fourth Edition, Mosby Year Book Inc. 1991.
- [5]. Brunner & Siddarth – Text Book of Medical Surgical Nursing, Seventh Edition, Published by J.B. Lippincott Company, 1992.
- [6]. Grinder. R.E., Adolescence Second Edition, New York, John Wiley & Sons, 1978.
- [7]. Julia. B. George, - Nursing Theories, The Base for Professional Practice, Fourth Edition, Appleton & Lange Norwalk, Connecticut Publications, California, 1999.

- [8]. Kothari. C. R., Research Methodology, Methods & Techniques, New Delhi, Wiley Easter Ltd., 1990.
- [9]. Luckman, Sorenson - Medical Surgical Nursing, Fourth Edition, Philadelphia; W.B. Saunders Company, 1992.
- [10]. Mudaliar & Menon's – Text Book of Clinical Obstetrics – Ninth Edition, Orient Langman Pvt Ltd., Chennai, 2002.